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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D2.2 Stakeholder consultation process mid-term report

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Stakeholder consultations were devised as a new engagement modality for the renewed iteration of the StandICT.eu project. The rationale behind them is to ensure StandICT.eu 2026's positions are well aligned with other European initiatives and important stakeholders, and further cement StandICT.eu as the go-to project and platform for ICT standardisation in Europe.

This deliverable presents the main findings of the first part of the process, both regarding the adopted method and the consultation outcomes. At M18, the outcome of the first large stakeholder consultation process is a positive one. The consultation was based on a recent project deliverable, a research report looking into Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape (D2.1). Close to 100 stakeholders were engaged, with tangible comments and suggestions distributed across different themes:

- Inclusiveness aspects;
- New Legislative Framework & digital sovereignty considerations;
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Market concentration & geopolitical considerations;
- Functioning of ESOs;
- Open-source considerations;
- Softwarisation of society.

This deliverable serves as the basis for the renewed version of D2.1, and will enable the StandICT.eu consortium to better shape its positioning on the ideas expressed in the report. Looking ahead, a second large stakeholder consultation will take place during the second part of the project's course – and will be reflected upon in the second version of this report at M36. Some findings, but also shortcomings, of this first consultation are addressed in this deliverable and will be tackled for a better process in the next months.

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ABBREVIATIONS

3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
AI	Artificial intelligence
CEN-CENELEC	European Committee for Standardisation / European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
DIGITAL SME	European DIGITAL SME Alliance
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EEA	European Economic Area
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
ESO	European Standards Organisation
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ETUC	European Trade Union Confederation
FOREST	Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable and Non-Discriminatory Terms
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NLF	New Legislative Framework
PMB	Partners Management Board
R&I	Research & Investment
SBS	Small Business Standards
SDN	Software-defined networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SMP	Single Market Program

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

As the second re-iteration of a now well-established project¹, StandICT.eu 2026 aims to continuously update its processes, and expand its scope of activities. Its core objective remains the same: bolster the European ICT standardisation ecosystem, with a particular outlook on supporting European experts' work at international level.

In that capacity, many of the project's cornerstone activities remain untouched – albeit, reinforced. Namely, the Fellowship programme provides financial support to European standardisation experts. 2 925 000 € is made available across the 36-month course of the project, through 9 Open Calls. A series of other initiatives support this programme, with the overall aim of consolidating a structured community of ICT standardisation experts around the StandICT.eu platform. Some were pre-existent to StandICT.eu 2026 (such as the Standards Academy, launched under StandICT.eu 2023²), others made their way into the renewed project.

The stakeholder consultation process is one of such new means to consolidate StandICT.eu 2026's outreach to the European ICT standardisation ecosystem. Taking inspiration from what already exists in European institutional processes³, the ambition for these consultation processes is to establish StandICT.eu 2026 as one of the go-to central ecosystem players, to which other stakeholders involved in ICT standardisation can refer to. By consulting a large base, StandICT.eu 2026 can:

- Refine its own analysis and work, by taking on valuable input and critical feedback, ultimately leading to better outputs for the ICT standardisation community the project serves;
- Nurture synergies with the rest of the European ICT standardisation ecosystem, bringing different stakeholders together around various initiatives.

As such, the defining and conducting of these stakeholder consultation processes is an integral part of the project's Work Package 2 ('Observatory and Technical Working Groups'). Two large consultation processes are planned for under StandICT.eu 2026. This deliverable offers an

¹ The initial project was launched in 2018, with a first re-iteration in 2020.

² <https://www.standict.eu/euos-academy>

³ See, for example, the Summary Report of the Public Consultation on the European Commission's Draft Stakeholder Consultation Guidelines: https://ec.europa.eu/smart-regulation/impact/docs/contributions/summary_responses_stakeholder_consultation_guidelines_public_consultation_en.pdf

overview of the work conducted over the first half of the project, and will be complemented by a second report at the end of the project's course.

1.2 Structure

The Report reads as follows:

- **Chapter 1** serves as an introduction to the document, presenting its scope, structure & relation with the project's other deliverables;
- **Chapter 2** presents the followed methodology for the stakeholder consultation process, defined in alignment with the project's External Advisory Group;
- **Chapter 3** expands upon the first large consultation initiated, on a deliverable produced by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape'⁴) at M16;
- **Chapter 4** offers some preliminary conclusions and learnt lessons, aiming to further reinforce the stakeholder consultation process activities in the second half of the project's course.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

This Mid-Term Report will be updated at M36, at the closure of the project, in D2.3 (Stakeholder Consultation Process – Final Report). In addition, this document should also be taken into close consideration with the following deliverables:

- D2.1 ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape'), on which the first large consultation process was conducted. The document is a research report based on 30 interviews with high-level experts in the field of ICT standardisation and drawing an analytical reflexion on the state of the European ICT standardisation ecosystem, as well as preliminary recommendations;
- D2.4 ('Update of Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape'), which will address the reflexions made by the consulted stakeholders on D2.1, as well as integrate a series of case studies;
- D5.1 ('Stakeholder engagement mid-term report') and D5.2 ('Stakeholder engagement final report'), which provide an overview of the more comprehensive stakeholder engagement activities of the project – of which the stakeholder consultation process is a part of;
- D6.6 ('Proposed Sustainability Framework'), which puts forward StandICT.eu's long-term sustainability strategy and on which various stakeholders will be consulted upon in order to establish a value proposition that can satisfy the wider ICT standardisation community on the long run.

⁴ This research report (D2.1) is not yet published on the StandICT.eu website at time of writing, but was shared with the different stakeholders that will be presented in the following chapters.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the stakeholder consultation process was defined during the monthly Work Package 2&3 meetings of the consortium. StandICT.eu 2026's grant agreement foresees two large consultations: one before M18, and the other in the latter part of the project and until M36.

As such, the Terms of Reference for the consultation process were defined in the earlier stages of the project, before being officially presented to StandICT.eu 2026's External Advisory Group for its review in November 2023. After receiving several comments from members of the External Advisory Group, the Terms of Reference were formally approved in December 2023.

The following subsections present the defined target documents, audiences, and feedback process for the stakeholder consultation process.

2.1 Target Documents

The Stakeholder Consultation Process is aimed to be carried out for policy-related or strategic deliverables of the StandICT.eu 2026 project. Other deliverables which are more internal to the project's operations do not fall under the scope of the process, since they are of little interest for the review of a broader audience. Specifically, such deliverables that would be concerned by the consultation process include:

- D2.1 – Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape
- D2.4 – Update of Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape
- D6.6 – Proposed Sustainability Framework

Official replies from the StandICT.eu consortium to European Commission consultations – or any other pertinent policy discussion – may also go through the consultation process, where relevant.

At time of writing, the first large consultation has been engaged on D2.1 – and will be expanded upon in the forthcoming chapter of the report.

2.2 Target Audiences

The Stakeholder Consultation Process is aimed to be conducted both internally to the project consortium, and externally.

Internally, all consortium partners (Trust-IT; Dublin City University; AUSTRALO; European DIGITAL SME Alliance; Fraunhofer; Open Forum Europe) should circulate the concerned document under consultation among their operating bodies and/or membership. In addition, StandICT.eu's External Advisory Group (EAG) should also be consulted, as well as the FOREST Group (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards).

Externally, relevant stakeholders with which StandICT.eu 2026 holds Memorandums of Understanding are to be reached out to. These include, among others, Small Business Standards (SBS), the International Association for Trusted Blockchain Applications (INATBA),

the Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI) and the OPC Foundation⁵. Based on the nature of the particular deliverable or policy positioning, stakeholders with more direct expertise on the topic will be prioritised for their input.

A key target group in this process are the Standards Development Organisations (SDOs), with which the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium has established consistent interaction. StandICT2026 is indeed presented biannually to the STAIR committee, comprising around 20 SDOs. Additionally, for specific topics such as the metaverse, consortium partner Dublin City University has proactively engaged with international bodies like ISO, IEC, ITU, and IEEE to connect with relevant technical committees and experts. As of the writing of this deliverable, we have directly consulted those SDOs and entities with whom we hold Memorandums of Understanding. After implementing the received feedback, the consortium will also evaluate the possibility to run a second round of feedback from SDO stakeholders without formal agreements to enhance the robustness of our final recommendations. This deliverable also integrates various recommendations from D2.1 particularly aimed at SDOs (detailed in Chapter 3), For all these reasons the present deliverable is also submitted as a proof of achievement of Milestone MS09 (M18) "Interim recommendations with SDOs and EU prioritisation."

2.3 Feedback Process

DIGITAL SME (as task leader) is to initiate the launch of the consultation process, after alignment with the rest of the consortium partners during a Partners Management Board (PMB) meeting. Consensus is to be reached with the other partners on both the particular document subject to consultation, and the list of external stakeholders to prioritise in the outreach. Based on the specific nature of the document, feedback expectations may vary. This serves to enable a better quality of input for each consultation process.

The document for consultation is then to be circulated to the consulting parties forementioned in Section 2.2. A deadline of two working weeks will be given for comments, with the possibility to further present the document in detail during a dedicated meeting if requested. DIGITAL SME is to collect all received feedback and arrange it analytically for the benefit of the lead author of the original document.

If disagreement arises with a third consulting party on some of the document's provisions, DIGITAL SME and the project partner leading the document under consultation shall attempt to resolve it bilaterally through a follow-up clarification call.

Consensus is aimed for. However, if impossible to reach, an addendum can be added at the end of the revised document onboarding the received feedback, stating that the document under consultation does not reflect the objecting party's position despite being actively consulted on the matter.

⁵ A full list of the outreached projects and organisations with which StandICT.eu 2026 holds a Memorandum of Understanding, and effectively outreached to, will be presented in the following chapter.

3. PROCESS & RESULTS

The first large stakeholder consultation process was launched at M16 of the project, on a StandICT.eu research report titled ‘Europe’s place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape’.

Close to 100 stakeholders were outreached, spanning from different circles: DIGITAL SME’s Working Group Standards (composed of SMEs involved or interested in ICT standardisation), members of StandICT.eu 2026’s External Advisory Group and FOREST Group (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards), projects or organisations with which StandICT.eu 2026 holds a Memorandum of Understanding, and finally the Annex III Organisations – mandated under Regulation 1025/2012⁶ to represent societal interests in Europe’s Standardisation System.

Comments structured around 7 main topical themes, in line with the core axes of analysis of the report and its derived recommendations:

- Inclusiveness aspects;
- New Legislative Framework & digital sovereignty considerations;
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Market concentration & geopolitical considerations;
- Functioning of ESOs;
- Open-source considerations;
- Softwarisation of society.

This Chapter goes over the process and its output, focusing respectively on the main aspects of the original report under consultation, the outreached stakeholders, and finally the received feedback.

3.1 “Europe’s place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape”

This research report was led by StandICT.eu 2026 consortium partner Open Forum Europe. It builds on 30 interviews conducted with experts in the field across the first half of the project (see Table 1⁷), offering a comprehensive analysis of Europe’s challenges and opportunities in the evolving ICT standardisation landscape.

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:316:0012:0033:EN:PDF>

⁷ Some additional interviews were conducted off the record, and are thereby not included in Table 1.

Name	Organisation	Profile
Jimmy Ahlberg	Ericsson	Company Standards Expert
Mirko Boehm	Linux Foundation Europe	Alternative Expert
Silona Bonewald	Leadingbit Solutions LLC	Standards Professional
Deborah Bryant	Independent	Alternative Expert
Jamie Clark	OASIS Open	Standards Professional
Debra Comparin	Thales	Company Standards Expert
Michael Eslamian	Huawei Technologies	Company Standards Expert
Jochen Friedrich	IBM	Company Standards Expert
Ashok Ganesh	CEN-CENELEC	Standards Professional
Chiara Giovannini	ANEC	Standards Professional
Daniel Haack	DIN - German Institute for Standardisation	Standards Professional
Kai Jakobs	RWTH Aachen	Alternative Expert
Théo Jaekel	Independent Expert (Standards and Human Rights)	Company Standards Expert
Konstantinos Karachalios	IEEE	Standards Professional
Mallory Knodel	The Center for Democracy and Technology (CDT)	Emerging Technology Expert
Tobie Langel	UnlockOpen	Alternative Expert
Arnaud Le Hors	IBM	Company Standards Expert
Alexander Prenter	Fair Standards Alliance (FSA)	Company Standards Expert
Dirk-Willem van Gulik	Apache Software Foundation (ASF)	Alternative Expert
Dirk Weiler	Nokia/ETSI (Retired at time of publication)	Company Standards Expert

Table 1 – List of interviewed experts in D2.1 (‘Europe’s place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape’)

While the purpose of this deliverable is not to re-iterate the analysis of the report, some of the main key findings and recommendations should be pointed out. Indeed, they constitute the bulk upon which consulted stakeholders were asked to provide their feedback upon. The key findings therefore focused around the three following axes:

- **Market Concentration and Standardisation** – where the report showcased that market concentration among a few dominant technology companies creates strategic barriers to open and inclusive standardisation. According to the report’s analysis, major players tend to avoid leading standards initiatives in areas they dominate, leading to fragmented markets and reduced interoperability;

- **EU Regulation and Software** – an area in which the report flagged that recent EU legislation in the technology realm increasingly relies on harmonised standards for implementation, and is expanding into the software realm. As a result, the report stresses that this places unprecedented demands on European Standards Organisations (ESOs) to deliver timely and quality standards;
- **Geopolitical Rivalries and Strategic Positioning** – where the report argued that Europe is under increasing strain to maintain its role at international level between American and Chinese influence. The findings further show that the EU's Standardisation Strategy ambition is challenged, given the necessity for international collaboration.

Derived from these findings, a set of preliminary policy recommendations were laid out. Beyond two more overarching recommendations (to first evaluate the impact of prioritising the quality of standards and inclusive representation in the standardisation process without compromising them for the sake of speed, and second to increase the demand for expertise of policymakers in standardisation to new sectoral areas such as software), the preliminary recommendations can be broken down into three main sets:

- **Recommendations to increase inclusiveness and transparency of the ESOs** – with calls for incentivising SME participation, promoting greater transparency in SDOs, and modernising transparency and access through potential revision of Regulation 1025/2012's Article 4⁸ to provide better access and feedback on standards;
- **Recommendations to increase the agility of the system** – with calls on addressing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) conflicts, increasing financial support to ESOs, updating the New Legislative Framework (NLF) to include software priorities; and expanding eligible ESOs (with notably the feasibility of creating a fourth ESO specifically focused on software);
- **Recommendations on open-source and standardisation** – with calls to include open-source in broader European research and innovation policies, and to create a Forum for open-source coordination gathering stakeholders from government, industry, academia and civil society to provide strategic guidance on open-source policies.

The report was formally submitted on 9th May 2024, date from which the stakeholder consultation process on it was initiated.

3.2 Outreached Stakeholders

In total, **94** different individuals were outreached for the consultation of this report, spread across different stakeholder categories.

As planned for in the Terms of Reference, presented earlier in Chapter 2, both internal and external stakeholders were consulted. Internally, DIGITAL SME's Working Group on Standards (constituted of its members involved in standardisation work) was actively consulted via a group presentation, and follow-up email communications. StandICT.eu 2026's External

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2012/1025/oj>

Advisory Group, and also its FOREST Group (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards) were also consulted. Externally, StandICT.eu 2026's 22 projects or organisations with which it holds Memorandums of Understanding were contacted about the report for feedback. Last, due to the strong inclusiveness component of the report, it was decided among the project consortium to also actively reach out to each of the Annex III Organisations.

Figure 1 gives a visual overview of the main outreached stakeholders.

Figure 1 – Outreached stakeholders per grouping

3.2.1 Internal Partners

Internally, the report was shared and presented across the memberships of the project partners with such relevant memberships to be consulted upon. In the project, two of the partners have such ties to members and supporting companies: DIGITAL SME on the one hand (with a network of 45 000 SME companies, distributed across different national and regional European SME associations⁹), Open Forum Europe (with supporting companies and other associations in the open-source realm¹⁰) on the other.

Considering Open Forum Europe is the lead author of the report, the input of its network was already considerably integrated into its analysis and findings. Many of the interviewed experts (see Table 1 above) emanate from its network and the broader open-source community.

DIGITAL SME presented the report on 17 May 2024 to its Working Group Standards, which regroups its members involved and/or interested in standardisation. The Working Group is **composed of 50+ members**, some of which are experts financially supported by Small

⁹ <https://www.digitalsme.eu/about/members-and-partners/>

¹⁰ <https://openforumeurope.org/supporters-and-partners/>

Business Standards' (SBS) annual call for SME experts in standardisation. DIGITAL SME is a founding member of SBS, and implements its ICT sectoral approach each year. As such, the Working Group Standards is jointly held with SBS.

The report was presented with a supporting PowerPoint, jointly prepared with some of the authors of the report at Open Forum Europe. It was the opening point on the agenda, designed to trigger a longer conversation and debate among the members of the group (Figure 2). The report was presented in approximately 10 minutes, followed by over 20 minutes of discussion.

The report was further shared by email with the members of the Working Group after the meeting, with a set deadline for additional written comments.

SBS WG Digitalisation / DIGITAL SME WG Standards Meeting

Date: 17 May 2024 (10:00-12:15)

Online – via [Microsoft Teams](#)

Agenda

10:00 – 10:05	Housekeeping Adoption of the Agenda Approval of the Minutes of the WG Meeting of 16 th September 2023 <i>Presenters: Massimo Vanetti / Alexander Chourreau</i>
10:05 – 10:35	Open Discussion: StandICT.eu2026's Recommendations Report ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape') <i>Presenters: Alexander Chourreau / Astor Nummelin Carlberg</i>
10:35 – 10:50	ETSI's new Director General selection – Process & outcome <i>Presenter: Massimo Vanetti</i>
10:50 – 11:05	Draft Position Paper on a Horizontal Market for Radio Equipment and Reconfigurable Radio Systems (RRS) <i>Presenters: Alexander Chourreau / Sebastiano Bertani</i>
11:05 – 11:20	Presentation on the final eIDAS 2 approved text <i>Presenter: Andrea Caccia</i>
11:20 – 11:30	Updates on ongoing work at the High-Level Forum on Standardisation <i>Presenters: Andrea Raffaelli / Alexander Chourreau</i>
11:30 – 11:45	CEN-CENELEC JTC21 – Updates on ongoing work in AI standardisation <i>Presenters: Alexander Chourreau / Emilia Tantar</i>
11:45 – 12:00	Projects Updates – BlockStand, StandICT.eu2026, Edu4Standards <i>Presenters: Justina Bieliauskaitė, Alexander Chourreau, Andrea Raffaelli</i>
12:00 – 12:10	ETSI SmartM2M Workshops on Data Act Standardisation <i>Presenter: Massimo Vanetti</i>
12:10 – 12:15	AOB

Figure 2 – Agenda of the DIGITAL SME-SBS Working Group Standards (17 May 2024)

3.2.2 External Advisory Group

StandICT.eu 2026’s External Advisory Group is a body of standardisation experts providing strategic guidance and orientation to the project. As such, it was deemed crucial to consult its members with the report.

The External Advisory Group was outreached to by email on 24 May 2024, with a short presentation of the essence of the report and the modalities for providing feedback. The possibility for a follow-up call or meeting to present the meeting in more depth was also provided. Additionally, on 10 June a reminder and brief presentation was given during one of the External Advisory Group’s regular calls.

The **10 full members** of the group, and the number of which gave a response, can be found in the below Table 2.

EAG Member	Affiliation	Answer (Y/N)
Ana Garcia Robles	Big Data Value Association (BDVA) - Secretary General	Y
Betty Xu	Seconded European Standardisation Expert in China Project (SESEC) - Director	N
Diana Dus	European Business School of Standards - Stakeholder Specialist	N
Karl Gruen	Austrian Standards - Director	Y
Lindsay Frost	Chief Standardisation Engineer - NEC Laboratories Europe	Y
Martin Chapman	Independent Consultant on EU Technical Policy & Standardisation	N
Sandra Drechsler	VDMA - Managing Director Technical Affairs & Standardisation	N
Sebastian Hallensbelen	VDE - Head of Digitalisation and AI	Y
Silona Bonewald	IEEE SA OPEN - Executive Director	N* <i>Prior knowledge of the report & participation in the interviews</i>
Stephan Weisgerber	DIN - Head of Digital Platforms	N

Table 2 – Members of the External Advisory Group

3.2.3 FOREST Group

The Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards (FOREST) is a recently set body to better align the technical work being done by the StandICT.eu Fellows with the set priorities by the European Commission. For instance, it monitors sensitive issues identified through the different Fellows, through an early-warning mechanism. It also seeks to build closer synergies and align the work of other standards-related European projects.

In this strategic capacity, the FOREST group was also outreached for feedback on the report. An email was sent out on 24 May 2024 in the same way as for the External Advisory Group, with a short presentation of the essence of the report and guidance for providing feedback. The possibility for a follow-up call or meeting to present the meeting in more depth was also provided.

Table 3 presents the full list of outreached members (**8 members**), and the response rate.

FOREST Member	Affiliation	Answer (Y/N)
Christian Grafenauer	Standards Expert	N
Dave Lewis	Trinity College Dublin	N
Diana Soeiro	Portuguese Business Ethics Association (APEE)	Y
Lindsay Frost	NEC Laboratories Europe	Y
Panos Kudumakis	Head of UK Delegation (ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29)	Y
Philip Maurer	CEN/CENELEC	N
Sandra Feliciano	Polytechnic Institute of Porto	N
Viveka Bonde	Bonde Advokater	N

Table 3 – Members of the FOREST Group

3.2.4 StandICT.eu 2026 Memorandums of Understanding

As defined in the Terms of Reference, it was also decided to engage all of the projects and organisations with which StandICT.eu 2026 holds a Memorandum of Understanding. While most of the projects or organisations work on very narrow aspects of standardisation, and are not necessarily engaged in broader policy and recommendations work, it was deemed a useful means to consolidate the ecosystem around StandICT.eu and bring a wide range of standards-related initiatives together around a common initiative and report.

As such, **22 projects or organisations** were outreached to on 21 May, with a short presentation of the essence of the report and guidance for providing feedback. The possibility for a follow-up call or meeting to present the meeting in more depth was also provided. Table 4 shows the full list of stakeholders, and the response rate.

Project	Project Area	Answer (Y/N)	
REINCARNATE	ReIncarnate	Digital transformation of construction	N
humantech	HumanTech	Digital transformation of construction	N
STAND4EU	Stand4EU	Manufacturing standards	Y
	CORTEX2	Metaverse	Y
NGI SARGASSO	NGI Sargasso	Future Internet	N
TeamAware	Team Aware	Emergency Systems	N
CyberSEAS	CyberSEAS	Cybersecurity of smart grids	N
PREDICT 6G	6G-Predict	6G Technology	N

	Drones4GREEN	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	N
	SMEunited	SME representation	Y
	EXA4Mind	Big Data	Y
	INATBA	Blockchain	N
	BlockStand	Blockchain standardisation	Y
	Edu4Standards	Standards education	N
	ELITE-S	Research Support	N
	BDVA	Data	Y
	AIOTI	Internet of Things	Y
	OPC Foundation	SDO	N

	OASC	Smart Cities	Y
	6G-IA	6G	Y
	COGITO	Digital Twins for Construction	N
	SPATIAL	Cybersecurity	N

Table 4 – Outreached projects or associations holding a Memorandum of Understanding

3.2.5 Annex III Organisations

So-called ‘Annex IIIs’ are organisations mandated under EU Regulation 1025/2012 to “encourage and facilitate an appropriate representation and effective participation of all relevant stakeholders”¹¹. These are permanently established, non-profit European associations representing specific stakeholder interests: Small Business Standards (SBS) for SMEs, the Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS) for environmental interests, the European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC) for trade unions, and finally ANEC for consumers rights.

Considering the analysis that was put forward in the report regarding inclusiveness considerations, it was deemed important to outreach to all of these organisations. SBS was informed of the report during the DIGITAL SME-SBS joint Working Group on Standards (presented above in 3.2.1) on 17 May, while the ETUC and ECOS were outreached by email on 30 May. ANEC was also reached out to by email, but had already been involved in the interviews supporting the analysis of the report (see Table 1, presented earlier in Section 3.1).

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2012/1025/oj>

Table 5 gives a full overview of the different Annex III organisations outreached to, and the response rate.

Organisation	Area	Answer (Y/N)
Small Business Standards (SBS)	Small and Medium Enterprises	Y
Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)	Environmental	Y
European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC)	Trade Unions	Y
ANEC	Consumers Rights	N* <i>Prior knowledge of the report & participation in the interviews (Chiara Giovannini)</i>

Table 5 – Outreached Annex III Organisations

3.3 Outcome

Comments structured around 7 main topical themes, in line with the core axes of analysis of the report and its derived recommendations:

- Inclusiveness aspects;
- New Legislative Framework & digital sovereignty considerations;
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Market concentration & geopolitical considerations;
- Functioning of ESOs;
- Open-source considerations;

- Softwarisation of society.

Figure 3 highlights these key comments, structuring them per main subfield based on the number of key suggestions received. The key suggestions are those highlighted in bold in the below subsections.

On top of these comments pertaining to the substance of the report, some stakeholders pointed out that the sample of interviewed people could have been more reflective of the diversity of the European ICT standardisation landscape. While these methodological comments will be taken on with the lead author of D2.1, they are not considered as a standalone subsection of this Chapter.

Figure 3 – Received key suggestions per main topic

3.3.1 Inclusiveness aspects

In line with one of the important sets of recommendations that the report put forward (*Recommendations to increase inclusiveness and transparency of the ESOs*), the first broad range of received feedback centred around inclusiveness considerations.

Annex III Organisations constituted the bulk of the feedback on this first point. Both ECOS and SBS stressed in separate contributions that, in addition to some of the examples of demands for better inclusivity and diversity in standardisation (C4.1 of original report), it would be pertinent to **integrate the Annex III organisation’s requests to ETSI’s governance review in 2022 (unpublished), as well as their recommendations on CEN-CENELEC’s**

governance review¹²). It was also encouraged by ECOS to **look into reports such as the Article 24 reports** under Regulation 1025/2012 (publicly available), which are more closely linked to any ICT specific actions Annex III organisations may have influenced over the past years.

The ETUC, SBS and ECOS jointly heavily **questioned the backing and lack of critical reflection upon one of the quotes attributed to an interviewed expert**, Mr. Jakobs: *“Umbrella organisations may not adequately represent the diversity within their constituencies, raisings concerns about the inclusivity of the standardisation process”* (p39 of original report). The ETUC clarified that all the standardisation areas in which it participates are supported by dedicated Task Forces composed of trade unionists from across Europe. These Task Forces are set up to share information and develop common positions on specific issues, including AI, thereby ensuring the large representation of the diversity of their constituencies into the development of standards. Similarly, ECOS requested that further justifications by third sources be added to such a statement, and if not to delete the sentence altogether if not substantiated. ECOS and SBS both stressed that the mere existence of the so-called ‘umbrella organisations’ under Regulation 1025/2012 improves the baseline scenario prior to the adoption of the Regulation. They also pointed out that it was unclear how this statement supported any of the recommendations put forward in the document. SBS further highlighted how Annex III organisations carry out their activity in a fully transparent manner (referring to the Article 24 reports¹³), and are subject to stringent evaluation, with annual Progress Reports and Final Reports, by the relevance European Commission and EISMEA (European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency) services. SBS also produces granular public annual reports of the technical work of its experts¹⁴, and in 2022 produced a Study on Priority Standardisation Areas for SMEs¹⁵. **Similarly to ECOS, SBS suggested to delete this paragraph altogether if not backed by other sources other than the attributed quote.**

More generally speaking, the ETUC remarked that the **use of the terms ‘inclusivity’ and ‘inclusiveness’ are used in an interchangeable manner** throughout the report, which may create confusion as to what these notions refer to. The ETUC **recommended to use the more consistent term of ‘inclusiveness’ throughout the text**, which is the most common term in the European Standardisation System.

Regarding the scope of inclusiveness, the ETUC further remarked that the **recommendation to ‘Increase inclusiveness and transparency of the ESOs’ seems solely addressed to SMEs**. It suggested to **further consider trade unions as well in such considerations**, especially in standards addressing occupational health and safety, work processes or work conditions, as trade unions bring in the workers’ perspective in standards development. This

¹² https://www.etuc.org/sites/default/files/page/file/2022-12/Annex%20III%20proposals%20for%20CEN-CENELEC%20governance%20review_Dec%202022%20-%20Published%20version.pdf

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/59134>

¹⁴ <https://sbs-sme.eu/?annual-report=expert-annual-activity-report-2022>

¹⁵ <https://sbs-sme.eu/publication/sbs-study-priority-standardisation-areas-smes/>

is all the more important since trade unions have no financial interest *per se* in participation in standardisation. Their engagement is only aimed at representing and defending the interests of their constituencies. Overall, the ETUC **agreed with the conclusion “that the European standardisation processes must evolve to become more agile and inclusive at the same time”.**

SBS suggested that **paragraph 4 of C4.1 (p36) could be better clarified**, since the wording of the paragraph is slightly misleading when discussing the “demand of increasing government representation in standardisation governance” after the Standardisation Strategy and Regulation 2480/2022. In fact, the national delegations from EU and EEA Member States already held, before this technical amendment, the voting power over the acceptance and proposals of work items for standardisation work in support of EC standardisation requests. The only tangible change concerned the fact that in the ETSI governance model, these decisions are now taken exclusively, rather than concurrently, by the national delegation.

Regarding the recommendation on incentivising SME participation, SBS commented that **foreseeing additional European funding streams under the current main financial envelope (SMP – Pillar III standardisation) would be counterproductive** and lead to an excessive granularity of measures put in place, potentially leading to a loss of impact of measures and initiatives currently in place. SBS supports exploring the possibility of additional funding for the participation of SMEs and SME-nominated experts in technical work under different EU funding chapters (eg: Horizon projects) or activating funding at national level by the Member States. In the coming months SBS will contribute with recommendations in this sense, leveraging the work currently being done under the High-Level Forum for European standardisation.

It also **disagreed with the reasoning of Research Recommendation 1** (*‘Investigate how Annex III organisations can be better supported to facilitate the inclusiveness of diverse voices into standardisation’*). While agreeing in principle with the idea of measures to support Annex III organisations facilitating the inclusion of even more diverse voices and expertise backgrounds in their work, SBS believes that **an excessive fragmentation of partnerships and incentives would lead to a loss of impact of the activity and initiatives currently in place** and make it easier to brush aside the voice and views of SMEs as too granular, isolated or unaligned.

Beyond the comments emanating from the Annex III Organisations on these inclusiveness considerations, other outreached stakeholders contributed to this strand of discussion.

The **6G-IA project agreed that more had to be done in terms of inclusiveness efforts for SMEs, and that this also related to some of the work being done under the scope of the project**. The **Stand4EU project advanced that there was a strong alignment between the remedies proposed by Stand4EU and the StandICT.eu report in the area of better involvement of SMEs, better transparency, and modern digital structures to ensure the effective participation of different stakeholders**. It stressed that the results in the Stand4EU project have indicated that not only financial incentives but also professional rewards and better access and transparency for newcomers are significant.

Members of the External Advisory Group indicated that it would be useful to **emphasise the European Parliament’s 2023 Own Initiative Report on a standardisation strategy for the**

Single Market¹⁶, which encourages the participation of SMEs to overcome market concentration – which is one of the core axes of analysis of the under-consultation StandICT.eu 2026 report. Another comment from the External Advisory Group highlighted that societal stakeholders are almost by definition “underfunded and understaffed”, which is a particularly blatant problem in high-tech fields such as AI and cybersecurity where experts expect high salaries.

Last, some members of project partner DIGITAL SME’s Working Group Standards regretted that the **inclusiveness section of the paper was relatively limited, and could have benefitted from further analysis**. This was, notably, deemed to be linked to the sample of interviewed experts – with very little representation of SME or other societal interest groups. Some also stressed that, regarding the recommendation on incentivising SME participation, the **main underpinning problem is that participating in standards-making is resource heavy and currently too few SMEs have incentives** to participate in such work.

3.3.2 New Legislative Framework & digital sovereignty considerations

Another strong strand of comments revolved around the report’s ideas on the New Legislative Framework (NLF) update, and related considerations around digital sovereignty.

One member from the External Advisory Group advanced the idea that the **NLF approach should be applied worldwide, and is a pertinent approach supporting digital sovereignty**. It was also suggested that aspects of digital sovereignty could be included in the European Commission’s standardisation requests. Another member of the External Advisory Group flagged the **growing gap between international and European standards – suggesting that better focus be put at international level**. It questioned if ICT needs are specifically European, and not more global – and thereby focus more on international-level standards making for European stakeholders. Discussing technical requirements and settling underlying issues should be done there as the prime objective.

While a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards broadly supported the recommendation on **updating the NLF**, SBS called to **better clarify the wording and suggested way ahead for this recommendation**.

3.3.3 Intellectual Property Rights

Intellectual Property Rights was a third important topic of discussion in the received input from the different targeted stakeholders.

A member of the External Advisory Group (EAG) called to **better reference and tie the discussed analysis to the Standards Essential Patents Regulation**¹⁷ in the section around

¹⁶ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2023-0136_EN.html

¹⁷ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/publications/com2023232-proposal-regulation-standard-essential-patents_en

Intellectual Property Rights (C4.3). Another member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards similarly suggested to **better clarify this whole section**, since some of the **wording around IPR and FRAND** (fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory terms) could be seen as potentially misleading.

Another member of the EAG pointed out that ICT standards have not been ‘non-open’ or ‘non-collaborative’ until now, and that **a sizeable shift to royalty-free cannot be observed for now, apart from the case of a few software implementations**. Most standards are FRAND (fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory terms).

A member of the FOREST Group lauded the report’s focus on the frictions between open-source and SDOs’ Intellectual Property Rights policies, and **suggested that the latter indeed need to be better revised**. It was however called to **soften one of the recommendations** (p46): “Our conclusions posit that while FRAND can remain the norm for hardware standards, royalty-free should be the norm for harmonised standards that are software-related”. Royalty-free implies no revenue, and no R&I incentives for companies. **A further development and analysis on this was called upon in the revised version of the deliverable**, with a recommendation for the European academic community to focus less on open-source but rather on more established patents. On the same topic, a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards **supported the idea that not only software-related harmonised standards should be royalty-free, but any harmonised standards**.

3.3.4 Market concentration & geopolitical considerations

A number of comments emanating from the External Advisory Group centred around two core and somewhat inter-related axes of analysis in the report: market concentration on the one hand, and geopolitical considerations on the other.

There was a broad call to **further clarify the assumption that market concentration allows firms to influence standardisation**. While it may occur, it is not the case by default. The use of **another quote, by Mr. Karachalios, was called out as out of context** and irrelevant to the scope of the analysis and suggested deleting it altogether: “Looking to the practices that this market concentration and lack of open standardisation processes enables, Mr. Karachalios sees a link “even to damaging effects on childhood” (p25).

On a related topic to market concentration, a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards pointed out that the **report put an acute accent on existing political pressures and new incoming regulations weighing on the standardisation system, while not focusing enough on industrial realities** which actually shape most of the carried out work and trends at standardisation level – considerations of which market concentration by some large players is an important part of the picture.

Regarding the geopolitical analysis of the report (Chapter C3.1), comments from the External Advisory Group noted that **the EU and the US have used global standards as geopolitical tools ever since the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) was founded** – and that such use is not solely the product of new geopolitical actors such as China. Similarly, it was proposed to also **explicitly mention India as one of the rising geopolitical actors on ICT standardisation**.

Another point flagged that despite the focus on global standards, often a technology has multiple good standardisation solutions and each could be mandated 'locally' with manageable costs for trade. The example of the various electrical plugs and voltages across different nations was provided. It was **suggested that the discussion in the report further explores the idea whether a given technology has strong network effects, or not.**

3.3.5 Functioning of ESOs: financial aspects, transparency & timeliness of standards

The functioning of ESOs was a cornerstone element of the report, and naturally attracted numerous comments from consulted stakeholders.

The **Stand4EU project consortium highlighted that while better financial resources for ESOs was not something that could be directly derived from their own studies, it played into some of the remedial measures that were extracted from the findings of the project.** Indeed, better processes and faster feedback times are in large part the result of better financial framework conditions.

A member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards stressed that **internal issues and bureaucratic inefficiencies linked to ESOs' functioning should be investigated before considering adding extra public resources.**

On the report's focus on speed vs quality, it was also noted by a member of the same Working Group that **quality of standards and inclusiveness are not necessarily opposed to speed and efficiency.** The latter are anyways an intrinsic and fundamental aspect of the digital field, due to fast-paced technological development. They should thereby be taken as a given under which other considerations such as quality and inclusiveness should not be sacrificed.

On the report's points on transparency of ESOs, while not disagreeing with the spirit of the request SBS **opposed the call to revise Regulation 1025/2012, including its Article 4.** As outlined in its [reply to the Call for Evidence on the evaluation of Regulation 1025](#), SBS believes in the overall fitness for purpose of the Regulation, and that efforts should be put towards the full implementation of its provisions (with a specific focus on Articles 5, 6 and 10), rather than proceeding with a revision of the legislation. On the same question of transparency, a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards pointed out that **publishing regular updates on ongoing standardisation activities does not solve transparency issues at CEN-CENELEC per se** – which is more of a closed system, as compared to the ETSI system for example where it is easier to get informed.

Last, one comment emanating from the External Advisory Group suggested to additionally **mention the issue of implementation costs which consumers may reject (such as cybersecurity measures) as an extra challenge** which ESOs need to navigate when responding to legislation – in addition to the already rightly mentioned challenges of various industry preferences, different political goals and the requests for inclusivity from new stakeholders.

3.3.6 Open-source considerations

Sixth, the numerous open-source considerations explored in the paper were discussed in length by several stakeholders.

The CORTEX2 project emphasised that **in software standardisation, there is admittedly often a need to use open-source standards, but these tend to also be mixed as well with proprietary solutions**. This is notably the case of their project, which is attempting to bring together a large community around a single standard of applications focused on XR-enabled collaboration and cooperation. On the analysis in Chapter 4.2, a similar line of thought was provided by a member of the External Advisory Group (EAG) on the fact that open-source necessarily leads to quick and seamless interoperability. Admittedly, and following the provided counter analysis, if everyone used the same code-base, this would be the case. However, **most organisations end up ‘forking’ an implementation to add an essential feature on top**.

Similarly to CORTEX2, the **6G-IA project linked the report’s discussion on open-source to its own work** – and notably a recent white paper on key strategies for Smart Network and Services¹⁸. It stressed the important role that open-source solutions may play for telecommunications cloud solutions.

Several other comments from the External Advisory Group also focused on these considerations. It was noted that **the general emphasis across the report that open-source stakeholders do not fit the traditional multi-stakeholder model are somewhat unclear**, since open-source stakeholders include a large fraction of experts which tend to be seconded from major corporations – in other words, “traditional” stakeholders with full access and the resources to participate in the standardisation system. On the same line of clarifications, it was proposed that **early in the document there should be a clear emphasis that “open-source” broadly means that anyone can see and modify the code, but does not necessarily bracket with the idea that there are no patents requiring licenses to use some of the ideas that are implemented in code**.

It was also suggested to add a mention in Chapter C3.2 on the fact that “riding the wave of softwarisation, some standardisation experts even see “older style” standards being supplanted by code”, and that this was **a view that IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) has long championed**.

In Chapter 4.1, one of the paragraphs asserts that “on top of the strain put on the standardisation system following the perceived politicisation in the standardisation landscape, the intersection of regulation, harmonised standards and software is increasing the pace of the convergence of open source and standardisation.” One of the received comments by the EAG points that **while the point is valid, it is not strictly cause-effect. Softwarisation could precede by proprietary code** – the first decade of the 3GPP implementations was provided as an example of that.

¹⁸ https://6g-ia.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/6g-ia-position-paper_2023_final.pdf

Several members of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards generally **questioned the over-emphasis on open-source across the report**. To many of the members, open-source was certainly to be considered an important component – but only one component within a very complex sector. It was **suggested to have a deeper emphasis across the paper on the software industry (within which there are open-source considerations), and not solely open-source per se**. One member further highlighted that open-source is of strong value (raising the example of contact tracing for example, which was controlled by some large companies before having a better and more effective open-source implementation, or Linux). However, it should be stressed as **a tool among others, and not the prime goal of the paper**.

On that point, it was also raised by a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards that one of the core problems of open-source is the lack of coordination of it. In that view, the **suggested idea of a Coordination Forum could be a first step, however the real goal would be to have a platform which coordinates money flows into open-source standardisation work, and its prioritisation**.

3.3.7 Softwarisation of society

Relatedly to one of the comments expressed above from a member of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards, a lot of the feedback finally focused on the report's idea of a "softwarisation of society".

First, different comments from the External Advisory Group delved deeper into this topic. It was **suggested to add a line of analysis on the upcoming and increasing role of AI software in standards making**. AI is already applied to speed up research (discover new medicines, design new chemical processes) and optimize known technologies (design super-powerful integrated circuits, or further optimize known algorithms and spread efficiency gains across millions of applications). Increasingly it will be used to "run" the processes currently handled by humans in the areas of drafting specifications, designing test cases, defining suites of conformity tests, etc. On the one hand, this brings speed benefits, but it may become even more difficult to validate the results sufficiently quickly, resulting in "nodding through" standards that are formally perfect and timely but contain hidden flaws.

More generally, it was noted that **the large majority of standards are still outside of the scope of software**, and relate for example to quality of paints, safety of toys, construction materials, specifications for machine tools, etc. While the softwarisation of society is increasing, standards work still in large parts reflects a world dominated by physical products (p17).

A paragraph in Chapter 2.2 was deemed slightly unclear, and called upon to be clarified: "This is, according to some of the interviewees, a result of trying to technocratically solve difficulties stemming from regulation further extending into software, relying on a standardisation system built for hardware".

In Chapter 2.3, it was **suggested to clarify that software is a means of implementing services. Software itself is not necessarily standardised. Deeper analysis on the issues linked to updateable firmware, a particular difficult aspect for compliance testing, was also encouraged**. Reference to the work under the Radio Equipment Directive or the Cybersecurity Act was pointed.

Different members of the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards also deep-dived onto this broad theme of softwarisation of society. It was **generally proposed that the report focuses more closely to certain more specific subsets of softwarisation, instead of going for a broader aim which is difficult to cover in depth due to the immensity of it.**

Regarding the **proposal of a 4th ESO on software, the recommendation was opposed by several members of the Working Group.** It was flagged that having an additional ESO entirely devoted to software may be difficult to focus on for SMEs and SME organisations, which are already stretched thin across different ESOs and Technical Committees. Moreover, it was noticed that software is a crossing topic that can be addressed in various settings of the existing ESOs (and in particular ETSI). In particular, one member stressed that **separating software standardisation appears to be technically the wrong thing to do at the present time**; while in the past hardware and software were less integrated, in current systems the integration is making the two more and more inseparable. Different examples were provided to guide any future analysis around this: software-defined networking (SDN), software-defined hardware (such as micro controllers used for instance in machines and IoT systems), or matched hybrid hardware-software that can be found in popular applications like smart TVs, smart cameras, etc.

On the same topic, **SBS also flagged that it disagreed with the recommendation for a new ESO focusing on software, and for Research Recommendation 2 of the paper**, following a similar line of thought as some of the members of the forementioned Working Group. An expansion of the field of eligible ESOs would lead to an excessive fragmentation and granularity of the system. The voice of SMEs and SME-nominated technical experts would be even more isolated, and the existing resources stretched even thinner. Furthermore, the excessive proliferation of the number of standards is already a very real problem for SMEs in terms of identifying the “right” standards to use and implement. A further expansion of the number of standards in this sense would lead to even further dispersion and confusion.

4. LESSONS LEARNT & NEXT STEPS

The rationale behind the consultation process is to ensure StandICT.eu 2026's positions are well aligned with other European initiatives and important stakeholders. Altogether, the initial aim when drafting the Terms of Reference for the process was to further cement StandICT.eu's position as the go-to project and platform for ICT standardisation in Europe.

At M18, the outcome of the first large stakeholder consultation process is a positive one. Close to 100 stakeholders were engaged, whether originating from specific constituencies of project partners (the DIGITAL SME Working Group Standards), some of the project's internal support and advisory groups (External Advisory Group and FOREST Group), external stakeholders with which the StandICT.eu 2026 project holds long-standing collaborations through Memorandums of Understanding, or other relevant third-parties (in this specific case, Annex III Organisations). Tangible comments and suggestions were distributed across different themes, in line with the analysis of the under-consultation report.

In the immediate future, the compiled received comments will be shared with Open Forum Europe, the project partner in charge of the original research report consulted upon. This will enable to address some of the concerns and suggestions raised by the different stakeholders in this process. Follow-up meetings with some of these stakeholders may be organised when need for further clarification on some of the suggested ideas.

Looking ahead, some lessons can be learnt to better shape the second large consultation process.

First, the given period (end of May-June) did not help in receiving more, or lengthier, contributions. Several outreached stakeholders apologised for not being able to look into the report in the substantial and rigorous way they would have liked to, due to the work overload they were faced with in this closing month before the summer break.

Next, the second consultation process could consider organising a large public event. This could be held online or in hybrid form in order to accommodate stakeholders coming from different locations. While a public presentation was organised in this case to DIGITAL SME's Working Group Standards, and the possibility for a more detailed presentation was provided to each consulted stakeholder, the given period of the year (as expanded upon above) likely did not prompt the willingness from the consulted parties to organise such a presentation and more thorough discussion for their members or teams. By organising a large public event, where each stakeholder could be invited to provide its input, this could further contribute to establishing StandICT.eu as a reference point for all ICT standardisation stakeholders.

Last, for comparability of the feedback between different stakeholder groups, it could be interesting to consider providing a formal template for the consulted parties to structure their answers along the same common lines as all the other stakeholders. In this first case, the rationale was to collect as comprehensive a feedback as possible, without orienting too much onto fixed questions. While the stakeholders were guided to the key parts of the analysis and recommendations, the lack of unified template for collecting feedback prevented the comparison of responses, and structuring it around centralised core themes. This could be considered in the future steps.

Taken together with the other flagship StandICT.eu initiatives on stakeholder engagement (see project deliverable D5.1 for more detail), this new initiative has so far led to better seal StandICT.eu's position as a referent voice on all ICT standardisation matters across Europe. The revised version of this report at M36 (D2.3) will now aim to onboard the learnt lessons, in order for a better overall process.